

Intestinal Subocclusion Due to Rapunzel Syndrome in a Female with Cerebral Palsy

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ABSTRACT

Rapunzel syndrome is a rare variant of trichobezoar characterized by a hair mass extending from the stomach into the duodenum. Management depends on the severity of clinical presentation and the bezoar's size and location, with surgery often being the preferred approach. This condition predominantly affects adolescent females with psychiatric disorders or neurodevelopmental delays, particularly those exhibiting trichotillomania and trichophagia. We report the case of a 19-year-old female with cerebral palsy who presented with nonspecific diffuse abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, and episodes of constipation. Imaging studies, including ultrasound and computed tomography, suggested the presence of a trichobezoar.

Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for trichobezoar in adolescents with signs of partial or complete intestinal obstruction, especially when associated with psychiatric comorbidities and a known history of hair-pulling behaviors.

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INTRODUCTION

A bezoar refers to a compacted mass of ingested substances that are indigestible or insoluble within the gastrointestinal tract (1). Among the different types, trichobezoars—composed predominantly of hair—are the most frequently encountered in humans (2). Rapunzel syndrome represents an uncommon form of trichobezoar, where the hair mass extends distally through the gastrointestinal tract, leading to partial or complete obstruction (3).

The name “Rapunzel syndrome” originates from the 1812 fairy tale by the Brothers Grimm, featuring a young woman with extraordinarily long hair. The condition was first recognized in the medical literature by Vaughan et al. in 1968 (4). Due to its rarity, the syndrome often lacks specific, pathognomonic symptoms, making early recognition challenging (3).

Typical clinical manifestations include abdominal discomfort, a palpable abdominal mass, signs of gastrointestinal blockage, involuntary weight loss, anorexia, and anemia (2), as observed in the case we present.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 19-year-old female patient with a known history of cerebral palsy and recurrent episodes of trichotillomania. She was admitted to our surgical department

following a one-month course of vague epigastric pain rated 6/10 in intensity, accompanied by nausea, recurrent vomiting, difficulty swallowing both solids and liquids, and episodes of constipation. These symptoms were followed by progressive abdominal distension, bilateral lower limb edema, and significant weight loss over the preceding week. The patient's family reported a history of similar, albeit milder, symptoms in the preceding months.

Clinical evaluation was challenging due to the patient's inability to speak—she communicated only through mouth sounds—and her marked aversion to physical contact with unfamiliar individuals. On inspection, she appeared pale with poor skin turgor, signs of dehydration and malnutrition, and alopecia localized to the right temporal area. Her hair was noted to be dry and thin; she was habitually seen wearing a cap. Abdominal examination revealed mild distension, a mobile and tender mass in the epigastrium and left upper quadrant, decreased bowel sounds, generalized tympanic resonance on percussion, and marked lower limb edema.

Laboratory investigations revealed profound hypochromic microcytic anemia with hemoglobin at 4.9 g/dL, and hypoalbuminemia with serum albumin at 2.1 g/dL.

Abdominal ultrasound and contrast-enhanced computed tomography identified abnormal gastric dilatation and an intragastric mass extending into the proximal duodenum,

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composed of heterogeneous material interspersed with air pockets [Figure 1–2].

A definitive diagnosis of intestinal subocclusion secondary to a trichobezoar occupying the stomach and extending into the proximal duodenum was established.

The patient's anemia and hypoalbuminemia were addressed collaboratively with the internal medicine team, through medical management and blood transfusions. After clinical stabilization, the patient was taken to the operating room for definitive treatment.

An exploratory laparotomy with gastrostomy was performed, revealing a 12 × 6 cm trichobezoar with a tapering extension into the proximal duodenum. The entire mass was successfully removed in one piece [Figure 3–4].

Postoperative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on the fifth postoperative day with marked clinical improvement. She was referred for multidisciplinary follow-up involving psychiatry, internal medicine, and nutrition services to address the underlying behavioral and metabolic issues.

Figure 1-2. - Computed tomography scan of the abdomen shows a big bezoar in the stomach and extension tail into duodenum.

Figure 3-4- A trichobezoar with a tail was surgically removed in bloc by laparotomy. 12*6cm

DISCUSSION

Trichobezoars are accumulations of ingested hair commonly located within the stomach, predominantly observed in pediatric and adolescent patients with underlying trichotillomania (5). While they typically remain restricted to the gastric cavity, cases in which the hair mass extends beyond the pylorus into the small intestine—such as the jejunum, ileum, or even colon—are classified as Rapunzel syndrome (6).

Gastric bezoars are considered rare findings, with a reported prevalence of approximately 0.3% during upper endoscopy procedures. Trichobezoars, in particular, are more frequently diagnosed in young women, especially those in their second decade of life (1). Despite the known association with trichophagia, only about 1% of individuals exhibiting this behavior develop a trichobezoar (3).

Several predisposing factors contribute to bezoar formation, including a history of gastric surgery (e.g., vagotomy or pyloroplasty), impaired gastric motility, and the use of

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specific medications such as anticholinergics, opioids, aspirin, nifedipine, psyllium, or wheat dextrin. Additional contributors include inadequate mastication, dehydration, high-fiber diets, diabetes mellitus, and underlying psychiatric disorders (1).

In many cases, patients remain asymptomatic for extended periods. Clinical symptoms typically emerge as the trichobezoar enlarges, potentially leading to partial or complete gastrointestinal obstruction (2). Initial complaints often include vague abdominal discomfort, ranging from mild to severe cramping, sensations of bloating or fullness, nausea, and vomiting—reflecting the body's attempts to expel the indigestible mass. Other common features include chronic anorexia and involuntary weight loss (5).

As the condition progresses, complications such as subocclusion or complete bowel obstruction may arise. Additional gastrointestinal manifestations may include peptic ulcers, bowel perforation, diarrhea, or even vitamin B12 deficiency due to bacterial colonization within the hair mass (3). On physical examination, findings are often subtle, though some patients may present with halitosis or a palpable abdominal mass. Notably, patchy alopecia may be observed in individuals with trichobezoars, often reflecting repeated hair pulling at various stages (1). Severe complications include gastrointestinal perforation, peritonitis, malnutrition, intussusception, and more rarely, obstructive jaundice, pancreatitis, or fatal outcomes (6).

Diagnostic workup generally includes imaging modalities such as abdominal ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Laboratory studies may reveal anemia or disturbances in serum electrolytes (5). The diagnostic gold standard remains upper gastrointestinal endoscopy, which allows direct visualization and potential biopsy of the bezoar, although this tool may not be readily available in all medical settings (7). Differential diagnoses should include gastrointestinal stromal tumors, pancreatic pseudocysts, and phytobezoars (8).

Patients presenting with gastrointestinal obstruction or active gastrointestinal bleeding due to bezoars require prompt surgical intervention. In the absence of these complications, management strategies depend on the clinical presentation and specific characteristics of the bezoar.

Trichobezoars are notably resistant to enzymatic or chemical dissolution, often necessitating mechanical removal either via endoscopy or surgical means (1). When the mass is large or associated with complications—such as obstruction or extension beyond the stomach—laparotomy or laparoscopic extraction is generally indicated (5).

Alternative methods, including extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy, enzymatic digestion (e.g., pancreatic lipase, cellulase), and pharmacologic agents such as metoclopramide, acetylcysteine, or carbonated beverages (e.g., Coca-Cola), have shown variable efficacy depending on bezoar composition and size (2).

Importantly, addressing the behavioral and psychiatric components is essential to prevent recurrence. Comprehensive psychological evaluation and intervention are necessary for patients with trichophagia or trichotillomania. Pharmacologic treatment may be beneficial in selected cases, particularly when psychiatric comorbidities such as anxiety or obsessive-compulsive disorders are identified (5).

CONCLUSION

Rapunzel syndrome remains an underrecognized clinical entity and should be considered in the differential diagnosis of adolescents and young women presenting with nonspecific gastrointestinal symptoms such as abdominal pain, vomiting, and unintentional weight loss—particularly in those with underlying neuropsychiatric conditions, including trichotillomania and trichophagia. Timely identification and appropriate intervention are essential to prevent life-threatening complications. Laparotomy continues to be an effective and definitive therapeutic approach in most cases, especially when the trichobezoar is extensive or associated with obstruction.

DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT –

The authors affirm that informed consent was appropriately obtained from the patient's legal guardians. Consent included authorization for the publication of clinical data and associated images. The patient's identity has been protected to the greatest extent possible, although absolute anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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